

north american
academic research

Research

An Innovative B2B ERP Model for Airline Travel Industry

Huma Pervez^{1*}, Anila Usman²

¹Department of Computer and Information Sciences- Pakistan Inst. of Engineering and Applied Sciences

²Department of Computer and Information Sciences- Pakistan Inst. of Engineering and Applied Sciences

***Corresponding author**

Accepted: 15 August, 2020; **Online:** 23 September, 2020

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4047195>

Abstract: In Pakistan Airline Travel Industry (ATI) is mainly working on B2B model where they procure advance bulk tickets from airlines and sale them to various agents spread all over Pakistan as well in Middle East & Arab countries under cash as well credit business models. In this research we thoroughly studied B2B business of one of the largest Airline Travel Company(ATC) of the country and proposed & implemented an Innovative B2B ERP Model. Implemented B2B Model Innovation includes multiple credit lines for ticket purchase / sale by agents, online & offline ticket sale & return channels facilities to agents, flexible income / discount facilities, multiple recoveries online & offline channels to agents. Paperless environment and used digitization for ticket issuance & return by agents.It includes real integration capabilities through API's ,Offline Bulk Import / Export and Scheduled Bulk data movement through DB tables using linked server/ web services with GDS / GL / any 3rd party system of the world.

Keywords: Enterprise Resource Planning, Business 2 Business, Airline Travel Industry, Global Distributed System, General Ledger

1 Introduction

The travel trade is one of the leading service industries in the world, increasingly important in the modern era. It focuses on the movement of people from one place to another, as well as on the services they need along the way, and is closely linked to the hospitality sector and the hotel sector, among others. In this paper, you will learn more about what the travel industry is and the implementation of an innovative B2B ERP model to perform its operations efficiently [1].

The Airline Travel Industry (ATI) suffers from a lack of generally accepted definitions, software communication standards, and industry data models that can be used as the basis for any travel

software. The development processes of information and communication technologies, in particular the internet, have revolutionized the entire Airline Travel Industry (ATI), spawning new business models, changing the structure of distribution channels used by the ATI, and restructuring all processes related to this industry, and, no less important, the impact to suppliers with vouchers, destinations and interested parties. E-travel combines some of the fastest growing technologies, such as communication and information technology, the hospitality industry and management, marketing and strategic planning.

Information and communication technologies (ICT) play an important role in the travel industry. The integration of ICT in the travel industry is vital for a travel company to succeed in the current global market. With ICT, a person can access travel product information anytime, anywhere. On the other hand, travel companies can reach target customers around the world with a click of the keyboard after mobile computers, web technologies, etc. have appeared. This research highlights the importance of ICT implementation for improvement. The level of competitiveness of the travel sector. It also explains the gaps between the impact of travel and ICT and suggests measures to address the gaps in Business to-Business (B2B) travel companies. Enterprise resource planning systems (ERPs) already account for the majority of information technology (IT) investments in large enterprises and trading companies. Recently, mid-sized organizations have also implemented ERP, with annual IT budgets in Europe reaching 500,000 to 50 billion [2]. ERP systems introduce enterprise information integration primarily by providing data integration and process provisioning between departments. This leads to the concept of business-to-business (B2B) customer integration in ERP.

The objective of ERP is to provide a platform for an organization's information systems and to make the company's business processes more efficient. However, implementing ERP systems is a huge job and most organizations are investing more in their IT services for efficient, flawed, free and profitable activities. ERP typically enables the organization to reduce inefficiencies and streamline the business process by allowing access to information from different parts of the organization.

In this research, we proposed an innovated ERP model for ATI. This ERP system auto integrated with 3rd party GL, Account Receivable Account Payable Modules. This ERP also real time integrated with one of TOP GDS's of the world i-e Galileo, Amadeus & Sabre. ERP is also integrated with Gmail (Email services) and SMS 3rd party software.

In this paper, we proposed an Innovative B2B Enterprise Resource Planning System (ERP) Model and system for Airline Ticketing Travel Companies (ATTC). Scientific contribution of this research are:

- Identification of major drawbacks in existing system and proposal of Key innovations into system
- Proposal of new Model / System
- Proposal of recommended infrastructure for the system
- Implementation of proposed system

Rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section II have the description of the selected case study, In section III, the identification of major drawbacks in existing system are discussed and Key innovations into system are proposed. Section IV includes proposal of new Model / System. Section V discussed proposed suitable infrastructure of innovative ERP model/system. Section VI, included Implementation of proposed B2B ERP Model / System for ATTC. In Section VII, results are discussed while the conclusions and the future recommendations are provided in the last section.

2 AN INNOVATIVE B2B SOLUTION - A CASE STUDY

In this research we selected one of the largest Pakistani ticketing organization that is doing B2B Ticketing Business. Sonya Southern Travels Network (STN) is the largest Airline Travel Trade finance, Tours, Umrah and Hajj network with 23 branches in all the major cities of Pakistan. Sonya Southern Group Travel wing specializes in the Travel, Trade and Tours Business. For the past twenty seven years, Southern Travel Network is consistently the leading group in the travel industry of Pakistan. In the year 2009-10 STN has had the privilege of providing travel and tour services to more than 125,000 passengers from and to different parts of the world, making the Sonya Southern group the largest contributor to travel from Pakistan [3].

In Travel Trade & Finance Sonya Travels (ST) is mainly working on B2B model where they procures advance bulk tickets from airlines and sale them to various agents spread all over Pakistan as well in Middle East & Arab countries under cash as well credit business models. In this model ST is offering variety of products to its various local as well as international customer for bulk ticket sale & purchase on very economical prices. ST Major products are listed below.

- TKT Sale & Purchase on CASH.

- TKT Sale & Purchase on 7 Days Credit.
- TKT Sale & Purchase on 15 Days Credit.
- TKT Sale & Purchase on 30 Days Credit.
- TKT Sale & Purchase on Advance Deposit (Through Debit ID's).
- Umrah Packages.
- Tour Packages.
- Hajj Packages.

Figure 1 shows that How STN business is dealing with agents and airlines.

Figure 1 : B2B Model of STN

3 IDENTIFICATION OF MAJOR DRAWBACKS IN EXISTING SYSTEM AND PROPOSAL OF KEY INNOVATIONS INTO SYSTEM

After through study, discussion and research on SNT we identified major shortcomings in their existing system and proposed an innovative model to them as per their business need as well as this model will be useful for any ATTC to help them to increase their revenue and strength the business. This model is named as AASolutions.

Figure 2 : Identified Issues in Existing System

In this section we will discuss about the issues and short-comings of existing ERP system due to which company was suffered a lot and unable to generate revenue as per business model. Figure 2 shows major deficiencies in existing STN system due to which company was badly suffered and unable to facilitate agents as per business need through proper model. Major Drawbacks in existing B2B system are listed below.

1. System Issues

- a. No Customer Relationship Management: Multiple CRM are opened against single customer and company is unable to identify their total numbers of customers at any point of time that required manual and adhoc reconciliation that resultant poor CRM management.
- b. Unavailability of Multiple Credit Limit against single credit limit.
- c. Unavailability of online Ticket Management. Adhoc work around used. Resultant multiple variants developed for single item.
- d. Poor workflow management
- e. Inefficient business process

- f. Unavailability of user activity dashboards to any agents / user- Resultant Transparency and trust issue
 - g. User unable to track his TRQ after its submission
 - h. Unavailability of transaction log of any user
 - i. Unavailability of audit trail of any activity
 - j. Unavailability of accept / reject reasons visibility on any TRQ request initiator
 - k. Unavailability of auto SMS & Emails features on financial & non-financial events
2. Integration Issues: Unable to integrate with any GDS & other system of the world through any available technology hence used ad-hoc work around for offline ticket management where human intervention was required to run business operations.
3. Costly
- a. Too Many human resources required.
 - b. Infrastructure was very costly
 - c. Unavailability of flexible configurable revenue module (income / discount) that resulted major income loss / leakage • Not Digitized
 - d. Unavailability of digitization of any process
 - e. No paper less environment
4. Technology Issues
- a. Poor system control
 - b. Out dated technology
 - c. Loosely couple hybrid model
5. Security Issues
- a. Poor session's management
 - b. Unavailability of secure password management
 - i. No Two factor authentication

After detailed discussions with STN executives, Managers and all concerned stakeholders we proposed them model that will fulfill their business needs as per market standards. This model and system is named as AASolutions. AASolutions is not only developed for STN it also have capability to facilitate any other organization of same business stream. In Figure 3 our proposed key innovative elements are shown. Main innovations are listed below.

- 1) Customer Management: Single Customer will be opened for all types of business natures / categories.
- 2) Multiple Credit / Business Type: Incorporation into AASolution for STN as per there core business requirements.
- 3) Digitization of Business Processes
 - a) Paperless Environment An Innovative B2B ERP Model for Airline Travel Industry
 - b) Less human resource
 - c) Efficient processes
 - d) Automated SMS & email for intimation to all stakeholders
- 4) Online TKT Management
- 5) Dynamic / Flexible Revenue Model: Flexible configurable revenue model is developed for income / discount. It includes configurable options of income / discount on following dimensions of airline travel trade & finance business.
 - a) Customer wise
 - b) Branch Wise
 - c) Airline Wise
 - d) Transaction Wise
 - e) Supplier wise
 - f) GDS wise, PCC, Credit Type wise, Sector, Class, Flown date, Origin, Destination etc.
- 6) Integration: System is online integrated with following systems and capable to integrate with any system of the world through API & other integration ways.
 - a) Galileo [4]
 - b) Amadeus [4]
 - c) Sabre [4]
 - d) HBL
 - e) GMAIL
 - f) SMS Vendor
 - g) General Ledger
 - h) Catalyst
- 7) Technology: Following items are addressed / implemented into system.
 - a) Technology migration from outdated desktop version to updated / new web technology.

- b) Multiple loosely coupled system developed in different tools technologies are migrated into single centralized system with all business requirement addressed. Now users can perform all its operations from single system. Operations includes.
 - i) Transaction Processing.
 - ii) Reports Extractions
 - iii) Process execution monitoring
 - iv) Integration with other systems
- 8) Performance Improvement
- 9) Controlled System
- 10) System Log / Audit Log
- 11) Cost Effective

Figure 3: Key Innovations for STN Business Model

4 ARCHITECTURE OF PROPOSED MODEL / SYSTEM- AASOLUTIONS

In this section we will discuss our proposed system that has been implemented during that research. We named that ERP system is AASolutions. Figure 4 shows an innovative B2B ERP model that is named as AASolutions Figure 5 shows, a complete block diagram of AASolutions. In Figure 6 AASolutions Core entities are shown This ERP system combines following key modules.

- Customer Management.
- Supplier Management.
- Master Configuration Management. It will contains all master configuration setups that will maintain by authorized user only.
- Revenue Module. (Income / Discount).
- Credit Management.
- Online & Digitized Ticket Management.
- Offline Ticket Management.
- Express Channels for On-call Offline Ticket Management.
- Group Seat Procurement & Selling Management.
- EMD Ticket Management.
- Airline Incentive Management.
- Bulk Upload Channels for Ticket Management.
- Auto SMS & Emails Configuration Management.
- Online Recoveries Management.
- Offline Recoveries Management.

Figure 4: Innovative B2B ERP Model - AASolutions ERP

Figure 5: Block Diagram of AASolutions ERP

Figure 6: Core Entities of AASolutions ERP

5 PROPOSAL OF RECOMMENDED INFRASTRUCTURE FOR THE SYSTEM

In this section, we will talk about the infrastructure of AASolutions ERP system. We get the quotation of three different vendors and based on security, client, performance, cost and preference we selected Cybernet (RapidCompute). RapidCompute have following certifications in providing cloud based service within Pakistan [5].

- PCI-DSSv3.2.1 Certificate
- ISO 27001:2013 Certificate
- GDPR Certificate
- PCIDSSv3.2.1 Checklist
- ISO 27001 Checklist

AASolutions final infrastructure details are shown in Table 1

Table 1: AASolutions Infrastructure Details

Application Server Details	DB Server Details
1. IIS (Version - 10.0.14393.0)	1. DBMS : SQL Server 2014
2. OS : Window Server 2016 Standard	2. OS : Window Server 2016 Standard
3. Hardware : Processor :Intel ® Xeon CPU E5-2640 v4 @ 2.4 GHz (6 Processors) Installed RAM : 24.0 GB	3. Hardware : Hardware : Processor :Intel ® Xeon E5-2640 v4 @ 2.4 GHz (8 Processors) Installed RAM : 48.0 GB

6 IMPLEMENTATION OF AASOLUTION PROPOSED SYSTEM

As we discussed in detailed that AASolution is an innovative B2B ERP system for ATI, this is cost effective, efficient, and transparent and digitized solution. With the help of that solution ATTC will be able to digitized there process easily and run their business smoothly and efficiently without human interventions. In this section we will discussion some major developed modules details.

6.1 Customer Management

Proper customer management is key feature of any ERP system. If system have proper and up to dated customer data then in future they will also be able to perform any time of analysis on it to forecast further business streams and decisions making. In AASolutions there is a detailed customer Management module available that includes following steps:

- Admin/assigned staff will be able to create new customer for each agent.
- Create user against each customer - create as many users as they want against single customer. This is the beauty of this system that one customer and use this system with multiple agents. Figure 7 shows customer Management interface of AASolutions.
- User will receive OTP and email through Two-factor sign-in. Figure 8 shows Multiple Credit Management interface of AASolutions.

Figure 7 : Customer Management of AASolutions ERP

Figure 8: Multiple Credit / Business Type in AASolutions ERP

6.2 Multiple Credit / Business Type

AASolutions is providing multiple credit type feature as this is main business stream of STN as well. This feature was implemented in a mode that other AATC can also use AASolution

easily. Each customer can be configured with multiple credit types as per their agreement with STN. Figure 8 is snapped of AASolutions Multiple Credit Management section.

6.3 Online Ticketing - Integration of GDS API's in AASolutions ERP

In this section we will discuss about AASolutions integration with GDS system in detail. Global Distribution System (GDS) platforms developed by the new Central Airline Booking Systems (CRS), first introduced decades ago. GDS have been the nexus of e-commerce in travel for decades, providing real-time virtual connectivity between thousands of travel inventory providers (airlines, hotels, car rentals, tour operators, cruise lines, etc.) and hundreds of thousands of retailers of travel products. Each GDS has provided airlines with a network of over fifty thousand stores worldwide and the ability to customize their offers and prices to meet market conditions. Currently, the three major GDS put together handle over 1.4 million travel transactions per year [6].

By this integration agents are able to perform online ticketing without involving ST resources and timely book and issue ticket to their clients. This is three steps workflow shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9: 3 Steps TKT Booking via GDS in AASolutions ERP

Figure 10 shows the search screen, by using this screen users have to enter the desired flight details and click on Show Flights button. After that system will interact with GDS and show the search flight details based upon integrated GDS results. Figures 11, 12 and 13 shows search results of AASolutions. User can book any flight by click on Book button from search results pages. Once click on Book button system shows results of Figure 14 After completing and submission of booking form system will return booked PNR details as shows in Figures 15 and 16. User can take the printout of booking details for their future reference sample shows in Figure 17.

Figure 10 : Search from GDS in AASolutions ERP

Figure 11 : Two-Way International Flights Search Results from GDS in AASolutions ERP

POWERED BY **SONYA**
A NAME YOU CAN TRUST

USERNAME: admin

HOME

MODIFY SEARCH

AIRLINES SHOW

STOPS SHOW

TAKE-OFF SHOW

FARE TYPE SHOW

Advertisement

 DXB 15:15 <small>Fri, 29 Jan</small>	PKR 34,611 Book Now			
Flight Details PK 211 Economy Discounted Refundable 0 Stop				
 KHI 11:55 <small>Fri, 29 Jan</small>	PKR 34,631 Book Now			
Flight Details PK 301 Economy Discounted Refundable 0 Stop				
 DXB 23:10 <small>Sat, 30 Jan</small>	PKR 34,631 Book Now			
Flight Details PK 213 Economy Discounted Refundable 0 Stop				
 KHI 13:40 <small>Fri, 29 Jan</small>	PKR 34,631 Book Now			

Figure 12 : One-Way Search Result through GDS in AASolutions ERP

jetset.pk/Online_Search_Book/Search

HOME

MODIFY SEARCH

ES

S

T CLASS

OFF DXB

TYPE

✕ Flight Details

DXB → KHI

Friday, 05 June | 0d 1h 55m | 0 Stop

ITINERARY FARE SUMMARY & RULES

DEPART

Friday, 05 June

DXB → KHI

0d 1h 55m

0 Stop

Friday, 05 June

13:30 — 16:25

DXB Airport → KHI Airport

DXB KHI

PK 208 Economy V

Figure 13: Search Flight Details from GDS in AASolutions ERP

SONYA
A NAME YOU CAN TRUST

AYAAN ELAHI TRAVELS
0300-9-0470000000-0505 | aayan@ayaanholidays.com

Home

ISB- Islamabad International Airport- (ISB) → KHI- Jinnah International Airport- (KHI)

0300-9-0470000000-0505 | aayan@ayaanholidays.com | 1 Adult

One Way Y

Depart: Wed 4 Nov

Home on hold

Customer Details

Credit Type: 15 Days Credit | Available Credit Limit: 90747.67 | Visa Type: Please select Visa Type

Enter Passenger Details

Adult 1

Mr. | Other Name: | Surname: | Male

Date of Birth: | MM/DD/YYYY | CNIC Number: |

Contact Information

Email Address: | Phone Number: |

Policies & Review

Total Payment to be made **14,228**

By clicking Book Now button you agree with Terms and conditions and money back guarantee. Thank you for trusting our service.

FARE DETAILS

Pax Type	Base Fare	Taxes
Adult X1	PKR20350	PKR2558
Total		14,228

Refund Policy
Any cancellation or changes made to this booking may be subject to penalty. Please check fare rules before proceeding for booking.
If any cancellation call service for more details on how fees for this flight.

Phone: 001-8466276
Mobile: 0300-9450000

Customer support available 24/7 worldwide!

Figure 14: Book Flights PNR on GDS in AASolutions ERP

POWERED BY
SONYA
A NAME YOU CAN TRUST

USERNAME: admin

Booking PNR Details!

GDS PNR: Q9MM4Q | Provider Code: IG

Remarks:

Supplier Code: PK

Name: Abid Ali

Base Fare: 50000

Flight	Departure	Arrival
PIA PK-212	16:30	20:25
Status: HK Class: Economy	Fri 1 Jan DXB	Fri 1 Jan ISB

PNR#:Q9MM4Q Generated Successfully.

OK

Figure 15 : Booking Result in AASolutions ERP

Booking PNR Details!

GDS PNR: Q9MM4Q Provider Code: IC7

Remarks:

Supplier Code	Supplier Locator Code	
PK:		
Name	Passenger Type Code	
Abid Ali	ADT	
Base Fare	Total Tax	Total Fare
50000	50000	50000
Flight	Departure	Arrival
PIA PK-212	11:30	12:25
Status: HK Class: Economy	Fri 1 Jan DKB	Fri 1 Jan ISB
Flight	Departure	Arrival
PIA PK-211	12:55	15:15
Status: HK Class: Economy	Fri 15 Jan ISB	Fri 15 Jan DKB

Save & Edit Cancel Booking Fare Backup Print Issue Ticket

Figure 16 : Booking Output in AASolutions ERP

localhost:57570/Online_Search_Book/Booking

GDS PNR: Q9MM4Q
Remarks:

Supplier Code

PK

Name
Abid Ali

Base Fare
50000

Flight
PIA PK-212
Status: HK
Class: Economy

Flight

Print 1 sheet of paper

Destination IT

Pages All

Copies 1

More settings

Print Cancel

Figure 17 : Print Booking Output in AASolutions ERP

6.3.1 Workflow of Online Ticketing in AASolutions.

In this section, we will define steps of online ticketing that are performed in AASolutions.

- B2B agents login into AASolutions with their login IDs
- Search desire flight details
- System will sent search parameter to GDS

- AASolutions save search log into AASolutions database
- System will return search response from received from GDS
- System will display search results to agents
- Agent will click on desire flight for booking
- AASolution will sent booking request data to GDS
- GDS Book PNR and send response to AASolutions
- Save GDS PNR response into AASolutions database
- Display booking details on AASolutions

7 RESULTS

In this section we will discuss the comparative results of AASolutions with old STN system. We divided our comparison in following categories:

- Cash Flow Generation and Increase in Income (Business Improvement via Technology):
Table 2 shows the feature wise comparison between old STN system and AASolution. It is shown that AASolutions help the STN to generate more Cash-flow, improvement in incentives, Discounts and yield management.

Table 2: Cash Flow Generation and Increase in Income

Feature / Dimension	AASolutions	Old System	Improvement
Cash Flow Generation			
Cash Flow Stream (due to subscription sale)	300 to 500 new subscriptions can be sold against security deposits to generate a quick 200M from the market	Poor new sales and old customers are returning their subscriptions	Cash Flow Generation
Increase in Income			
Switch Board / Control Screen (AL, GDS, PCC, Void Charges)	Yes - (We can quickly change GDS PCCs are per market/capping situation and reap quick profits)	No	Quick Profit Minting
Accurate calculation of sale/incentives/profits/disc outns	Yes	N/A	improvement in Incentive, Discount and Yield Calculation
Class-wise	Yes	N/A	improvement in yield
Sector Wise	Yes	N/A	improvement in yield
Flown date wise	Yes	N/A	improvement in yield
Visa type wise	Yes	N/A	improvement in yield

Feature / Dimension	AASolutions	Old System	Improvement
Multiple Credit Limit Options (and respective discount levels for every product)	Yes	No	Yield Management
Proper discount/psf rules enforcement (Exception handling facility)	Yes (Minimum loss of income, unintended discounts)	Frequent missing exception rules (resulting in extra discount for agents)	Yield Management
Monthly Services Fee/Per (up to 10k per agent) can be charged for additional services like (B2B2B Sub-IDs Module)	Base has been laid (it can be developed quickly)	No	Perpetual Income
Increased sale due to better services	Sales can be increased by 25% with an efficient new system	Many agents are not ready to work with our Edge System	Higher profits, Higher Market Share

- Cost Efficient / Cost Control: In Table 3 we can see that AASolutions is providing cheap solution as compare to old STN system. It will reduce STN cost by reduction in of Work/Human Resource Requirement, comparatively low price infrastructure and it can also save time cost due to its efficient processing.

Table 3: Cost Control

Feature / Dimension	AASolutions	Old System	Improvement
Accurate attribution of losses/ADMS/date change charges to agents or branches	Yes	N/A	Cost Control
Efficiency, losses and Operational Cost	Significant improvement in efficiency and operational cost with minimum losses	Lower efficiency, frequent losses at higher operational cost (Many unintended Discounts)	Cost Control
Infrastructure Cost	Medium (Relatively)	High	
Reduction in Work/Human Resource Requirement due to:			Cost Control (Gradually)

Feature / Dimension	AASolutions	Old System	Improvement
Rejection message / remark communication	Possible	Not Possible	
Multitasking (Multiple request handling)	Possible	Not Possible	
Two way messages facility (remarks)	Possible	Not Possible	
Need for phone calls	Limited	Extensive	
CRM System	Easy to develop based on this system +(Customized Marketing messages facility etc.)	Developed in a separate universe	Efficient and Better Work
CN/DN processing	Minimum Need (once system issues are resolved)	Frequent occurrence	Lesser work
Automated reports (in excel or access)	Yes	No	Efficient and Better Work
Integrated Power BI facility	Yes	No	Efficient and Better Work
Better Technology employed	Only Web-based interface for all operations	Desktop based (Edge) + Web-based B2B Application (Agent End)	Better system performance
Modules Integration (Front End/Application side)	Only one technology is being used so no chance of missing information	Loosely integrated modules (resulting in missing communication of requests)	Better system performance
Efficiency of Service and Agent Satisfaction	High	Low	Lesser work
Involvement of Branch Staff in operational Activities	Minimum	High	Lesser work
Visibility for Branches (agent activity, performance, discount)	Extensive	Limited	Lesser work

- Risk Control & System Efficiency: In Table 4 we can see that AASolutions is mitigating the maximum risk associated to any system and it is also much more efficient than previous one.

Table 4 : Risk Control & System Efficiency

Feature / Dimension	AASolutions	Old System	Improvement
Development, Test and UAT environment to users	Separate testing link (No Risk)	Live development and testing only (High Risk)	Risk Control, System Efficiency
Strict Credit Limit Enforcement	Yes (100%)	Many exceptional cases Frequent System Down	Risk Control, System Efficiency
Automatic Discount Calculation	Yes	No	Risk Control, System Efficiency
Proper intimation of every important activity (minimum chances of disputes)	Yes	No	Risk Control, System Efficiency
Two Factor Authentication System (w.r.t password set-up/change etc.)	Two-Factor Authentication for PW change	Limited (Ms. Asma sends a generic PW which everybody knows)	Risk Control, System Efficiency
Visibility of system usage/sign-in/sign-out (just like banks)	Yes	No	Risk Control, System Efficiency
Branch activity on behalf of agent is visible to agent	Yes	No	Risk Control, System Efficiency
Out of system ticketing	Should be minimum (most of the possible causes are addressed)	Frequent occurrence	Risk Control, System Efficiency
Business Process Documentation (visibility)	Yes	No	Risk Control
Sharing of Master Code Files (system framework access)	Yes, To Designated Personnel	No	Risk Control
Quality Assurance Levels	3 level (before going live) with signed reports	Live response (Usually agents inform us about a new feature deployment)	Risk Control, System Efficiency
Security (w.r.t password set-up/change etc.)	Two-Factor Authentication for PW change	Limited (Ms. Asma sends a generic PW which everybody knows)	Risk Control

Feature / Dimension	AA Solutions	Old System	Improvement
Firewall/Protection from hacking	Encrypted PW with Hashing and Salting. Secured Store procedures are being used for APPs and DB communication instead of in-line queries	Yes (Arguably)	Risk Control
Process based Cr. Limit Enhancement (with record)	Yes (within system request, approval and allocation)	No (Out of system, sms based requests and approvals)	Risk Control
Customer management/Address book audit log (activity trail)	comprehensive audit log	ineffective audit log	Risk Control
Visibility for Agency Staff (Status Updates on System Dashboard)	Yes	No	Risk Control, System Efficiency
Visibility for Agency Owner (SMS and Email)	Effective, Efficient and available on every activity	Limited/No or Ineffective	Risk Control, System Efficiency
Communication in case of rejection	Yes	No	Risk Control, System Efficiency
Quick Redressal of rejected query and resubmission facility	Yes	No	Risk Control, System Efficiency
Minimum Data Entry	Yes (With Data Parsing facility, To be developed)	No	Risk Control, System Efficiency
Updated and correct Ledger and statements	99% Correct	Partially Correct (90%)	Risk Control, System Efficiency
Correct discount calculation (without follow-up)	99% Correct	Partially Correct (90%)	Risk Control, System Efficiency
Reliability and Certainty (no unpleasant surprises, Ticket requests getting disappeared)	High	Low	Risk Control, System Efficiency
Record of communication/Remarks (to avoid	Yes	N/A	Risk Control, System Efficiency

Feature / Dimension	AASolutions	Old System	Improvement
discrepancy/disagreements)			
Self-service option for Void, Reissue, Refund	for void, reissue, refund	only for void	Risk Control, System Efficiency
Quick reimbursement in case of Re-issue, Refund (after AL approval)	Yes (due to system based framework with automatic check and balance)	frequent delays due to involvement of many departments including branches	System Efficiency
Self-service option for credit limit enhancement request	Yes	No	System Efficiency
Personalized Agent Screen (Agent Logo, Name etc.)	Yes (with improved design)	Yes	System Efficiency
Personalized Ticket Printing Format (Agent Logo, Name etc.)	Under development	No	System Efficiency
Technology specific Human Resources	Adequate availability of human resources	Limited availability of human resources	Risk Control

- Infrastructure: In Table 5 shown the advantages of proposed AASolutions B2B ERP system as compared to old system. In this Table we will see that with the help of new system company can save infrastructure cost and get more resources and optimized performance better than previous one.

Table 5 : AASolutions Infrastructure

Factor	Old Infrastructure	AASolutions Infrastructure	Advantages
Cost	\$12,444 / Year	\$10,800 / Year	\$1644 Less Payment on Local Clouds
Payment Term	Yearly Advance	Quarterly Advance (\$2700 / Quarter)	Flexibility in payment term
RAM	32 GB	72 GB	40 GB Additional RAM
Compute -Cores	8 Cores	14 Cores	6 Additional Cores
Storage	1 TB	1.5 TB	500 GB additional storage

8 CONCLUSION & FUTURE WORK

The aim of this paper is to optimize business process of one of the largest ticketing travel organization along with its existing implemented system and proposed an innovated model that will digitized the business process on Airline travel industry. It reveals that our proposed AASolutions improve the operation and business capabilities of travel agency. This research shows how the AASolutions positively change the B2B travel & trade business. AASolutions makes interfaces point-and-click which have renovated the online business. The paper shown that the old STN system had weaknesses which AASolutions successfully mitigated or resolved.

The paper shows that the AASolutions support each other's key and sub-processes for STN, which affects the company's operational quality. The integration of the most important processes and sub-processes enables the company to achieve a huge improvement in the development of technology. The most important results showed that after the processes have been optimized with the web-based system, the workflows/processes become more integrated and systematic. GL is a fully integrated system like GDS and helps the company become more efficient in meeting customer needs and keeping up with the changes in the market environment.

A number of basic flaws had been identified in the old STN system and these are resolved through the implementation of the AASolutions. The current system lacks the integration and connectivity to enable the business to serve its client more rapidly, and as a outcome, the company loses its customers and ultimately disturbs its profitability. With GDS web-based AASolution, the company can optimize existing processes where most of the activities are done manually. AASolutions enables the company to significantly reduce management costs and increase profit across all processes. In this way, the company has achieved significant operational excellence. This can be achieved in terms of decreasing customer complaints, reduced waiting and processing times, faster response to different customer demands and segments, and in particular better decisions for customers. Achieving operational excellence with the new AA Solutions compared to the old process provides enhanced protection for STN products and services.

Implementing AASolutions can reduce process rework, redundancy, duplication, task duplication, data collection and evaluation inconsistencies, and system inefficiencies. In addition, the case experience provided a deeper understanding of the employees and managers involved in making business decisions. In conclusion, the AASolutions enables the company to sustain-ably meet the current market demand and to be able to survive and retain its customers in a long run.

In fact, to stay competitive in the market, the investment in the AASolutions is a sensible resolution for the long-term strategy. Therefore, the systematic initiatives and integrated system for the STN would improve the company's opportunities to advance competitors in the market. The following recommendations are presented based on the aforementioned research.

- All modules data will be moved to BI & Warehouse for their reporting, E-Marking and vintage analysis.
- Implement recommendation system of proposed model. • With the help of warehousing and recommendation systems, organizations will be able to predict the business dimensions.
- By implementation of warehousing organizations will do Right Investment on right item on right time?
- Organizations can analyze trend purchases.

References

- [1] Travel Industry: An Overview of One of the Largest Service Industries [online] Revfine. Available at: <https://www.revfine.com/travel-industry/> [Accessed 15 JUN. 2020].
- [2] Van Everdingen, Y., Van Hillegersberg, J., & Waarts, E. (2000). Enterprise resource planning: ERP adoption by European midsize companies. *Communications of the ACM*, 43(4), 27-31.
- [3] Sonya Travels GlobalStar Pakistan [online] GlobalStar. Available at: <https://globalstartravel.com/location/pakistan-sonya-travels/> [Accessed 15 JUN. 2020].
- [4] Satalkar, M. A. (2017). The Global Distribution System (GDS) as Future of Communication in Hospitality Industry. *KIMI Hospitality Research Journal*, 2(1), 10.
- [5] RAPIDCOMPUTE CLOUD [online] RapidCompute . Available at: <https://rapidcompute.com/> [Accessed 15 JUN. 2020].
- [6] Emmanuel, A. A., Oluwafunmilayo, O. O., Mobolaji, O. A., Abioye, A., Adedoyin, O. O. (2018). Perception of Travel Agents Towards Amadeus And Galileo Global Distribution System. *Canadian Social Science*, 14(10), 17-30.

Dr Anila Usman received her Ph.D Degree in Numerical Analysis from Manchester Univ, UK. Currently working as Dean of sciences in Pakistan Institute of Engineering and Applied Sciences, Islamabad, Pakistan. Her main research interests are Numerical Computing, Parallel/Distributed Computing Data Warehousing, Databases, Business Intelligence and cyber security.

Huma Pervez received her MS (CS) Degree from UIIT, ARID Agriculture University in 2017, she is currently Pursuing Ph.D in Computer Sciences from Pakistan Institute of Engineering and Applied Sciences, Islamabad, Pakistan. Her main research interests are Data Warehousing, Databases, Business Intelligence, Software Engineering and Blockchain.

Acknowledgments

All praises and thanks be to Almighty Allah. Much Appreciation to Pakistan Institute of Engineering and Applied Sciences for the Research facilities, and to the supervisor Dr. Anila Usman for her guidance and recommendations. I am deeply grateful to my father Mr. Pervez Akhtar for his immense support and high level of motivation throughout my study career.

Dedication

This work is dedicated to Mr. Abid Ali, Chief Information Technology of Sonya Southern Groups, for his kindness and devotion, and for his endless support of providing of case study details. And help us to understand the business steam of travel and trade industry during this research. His

knowledge helped us to get the in-depth knowledge of selected case study as he is part of that organization and his facilitation regarding knowledge sharing is very admirable.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

© 2020 by the authors. TWASP, NY, USA. Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

Assets of publishing with NAAR

- Global archiving of articles
- Immediate, free online access for all
- Rigorous peer review process
- Authors retain copyrights
- DOI for all articles

<https://twasp.info/journal/home>

A graphic of a green globe with a plant growing from the top, set against a background of radiating lines.

Submit your article : editor@twasp.info